

spacing 5.4-8.1% for 20 x 20 cm, and only 0.7-1.6% for 30 x 30 and 40 x 40 cm.

At the 10- x 10-cm spacing the increase in disease incidence was 171.1% from N₅₀ to N₁₀₀ but only 7.6% from

N₁₀₀ to N₂₀₀.

At the 20- x 20-cm spacing the increase in disease incidence was 137.4% from N₅₀ to N₁₀₀ and 29.1% from N₁₀₀ to N₂₀₀. ■

Data on sheath blight incidence in Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Sheath blight incidence (%) at spacing of			
	10 x 10 cm	20 x 20 cm	30 x 30 cm	40 x 40 cm
N ₀ – Full basal	–	–	–	–
N ₀ – 2 splits	–	–	–	–
N ₀ – 3 splits	–	–	–	–
N ₀ – 4 splits	–	–	–	–
N ₅₀ – Full basal	16.2	2.7	–	–
N ₅₀ – 2 splits	21.6	1.8	–	–
N ₅₀ – 3 splits	19.8	2.6	–	–
N ₅₀ – 4 splits	20.7	2.0	–	–
N ₁₀₀ – Full basal	51.3	4.5	0.9	0.8
N ₁₀₀ – 2 splits	59.4	5.4	0.8	1.0
N ₁₀₀ – 3 splits	52.2	6.3	0.8	0.9
N ₁₀₀ – 4 splits	49.5	5.4	0.7	0.8
N ₂₀₀ – Full basal	58.5	8.1	0.9	1.1
N ₂₀₀ – 2 splits	56.7	7.2	0.8	0.7
N ₂₀₀ – 3 splits	60.3	5.4	1.6	0.9
N ₂₀₀ – 4 splits	53.1	7.2	0.9	0.8

Rice blast — races or virulence frequencies?

K. M. Chin, Rice Research Branch, Malaysian Agricultural Research and Development Institute, Bumbong Lima, P. W., West Malaysia

A recent article on races of *Pyricularia oryzae* raises several interesting questions about the current state of understanding of the population genetics and dynamics of the pathogen (Wu, H. K. 1979. Rice blast disease in Taiwan — Race and variety resistance. Tech. Bull. ASPAC Food Fert. Tech. Cent. 48.).

The author advocated the use of the international differential set of rice varieties to monitor changes in the racial composition of blast in Taiwan. He concluded that “race distribution was stable” because the predominant races in 1975-78 were similar to those in 1966.

This conclusion is not necessarily valid because the race frequencies studied involved only the characterization of virulence frequencies corresponding to those of the international differentials. Substantial changes in the racial composition in Taiwan could conceivably have been detected if relevant local varieties had been used as differentials.

The author also commented that “a lot of labor would be saved” if the international differentials were used instead of 12-16 local differentials. Although the labor saving is undeniable, much important information might be lost. It seems more logical to concentrate in the future on the frequencies of relevant pathogen genes rather than on frequencies of largely irrelevant genotypes.

The paper further contended that the disease severity on a rice variety was determined by the “number of its existing virulent races.” A more accurate statement may be that disease severity is determined by the frequency of the corresponding virulence in the pathogen population. This virulence may be present in one or many races. That there is often a direct correlation between the number of virulent races (as determined by an arbitrary set of differentials) that can attack a variety and its susceptibility is merely a statistical artifact of the race concept.

If a variety is susceptible, it may be assumed that the corresponding virulence is high in frequency. There is then a correspondingly high probability

of it being combined with other virulences in the pathogen population. ■

Rice ragged stunt disease in Annamalainagar, Tamil Nadu, India

P. Narayanasamy and P. Baskaran, Entomology Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, Annamalai University Annamalainagar, Tamil Nadu

References to large-scale occurrence of viral and mycoplasmal diseases on rice have lately been frequent. During routine field visits at the Agricultural Experimental Farm of Annamalai University, the authors detected diseased and stunted plants (culture ARC5752 from IRRRI). The leaves were ragged and serrated, and vein-swelling was marked on the outer surface of the leaf sheath. Flag leaves were small, twisted, and malformed and showed incomplete emergence. Panicle emergence was incomplete and panicles bore mostly chaffy grains. Most of the tillers were branched and produced many panicles. Flowering was delayed and the diseased plant was totally unproductive.

With those characteristic symptoms the disease was suspected to be ragged stunt as described by K.C. Ling [IRRN 2(5) (1977): 6-7]. The disease is reported for the first time from this part of India; however, its occurrence in Coimbatore has been mentioned in a publication of Tamil Nadu Agricultural University. The disease is transmitted and spread by the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal. As the BPH population is increasing in the Cauvery delta, large-scale recurrence of the disease is possible. Hence, suitable prophylactic control measures will be taken up to reduce the BPH populations. ■

Studies on udbatta disease in Karnataka, India

S. Sanne Gowda, pathologist, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), University of Agricultural Sciences, Regional Research Station (RRS), V. C. Farm, Mandya, Karnataka, India

Udbatta disease caused by *Ephelis oryzae* has occurred in Karnataka State for more than three decades and caused

considerable loss in grain yield of local improved and high yielding rice varieties. Recorded observations show that disease intensity is generally higher during kharif in the cooler climatic regions than during summer in hotter climates. The disease has been observed in varying intensity at all altitudes. It is not specific to any soil type nor to paddy variety. Some varieties, e.g. IET1444 and FTB20, were

continuously infected during kharif; others – e.g. IET3626, IET5725, and IET4107 – had maximum disease infection in 1 year but were absolutely free from the disease during subsequent years. Thus, it is difficult to judge a variety for its susceptibility.

The studies on disease control by seed treatment carried out for several years at the RRS indicate that only the hot-water

treatment at 54°C for 20 minutes gives good control. Other studies carried out with systemic fungicides indicate that carboxin and carbendazim are second to the hot-water treatment in checking the seedborne infection.

Further detailed investigations on the etiology of the causal organism and its mode of infection are needed to understand the disease. ■

***Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv. — a new host for *Rhynchosporium oryzae* Hashioka and Yokogi**

S. Amu Singh and P. K. Sen Gupta, Plant Pathology Department, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswa Vidyalaya, Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal, India

During a search for collateral hosts of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* (the causal organism of rice leaf scald disease) severe leaf scald disease was observed in October 1978 at Takyel, Manipur, on the leaves of the graminaceous weed *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv. The weed was growing in a field of the local

2. Fungal growth on the PDE.

rice variety Chahao, which was also severely infected. The typical light- to dark-brown zonate symptoms identical to those of rice leaf scald disease as described in Japan were produced on leaf tips (photo 1). Each successive band was accompanied by narrow, light-brown halos. The average lesion was 2.58 cm long, ranging from 1-4.5 cm. Five to 10% of the leaf area was infected.

The fungus, when isolated in pure culture, produced luxuriant white growth on potato dextrose agar amended with 2% hot water extract of rice leaf (PDE) and copious bicelled, slightly falcate conidia within 4-6 days of incubation at 25±1°C (photo 2). The conidia were borne directly on the hyphae or on short conidiophores and they germinated readily in water within 6 hours of incubation at 25±1° C. The mean conidial size was 11.82 × 3.62 μ on the leaf lesions and 12.28 × 4.0 μ on PDE. The mycelium from the host tissue was hyaline, septate, and branched.

When artificially inoculated on the susceptible rice cultivar Jaya, the fungus produced typical leaf-tip blight, reddish-brown lesions on the leaf sheath, and

water-soaked lesions (like those of rice leaf scald disease) on the margins of the leaf blade.

A culture of the fungus, sent to the Commonwealth Mycological Institute, Kew, England, was confirmed as *R. oryzae*. This is the first report of a collateral host for *R. oryzae*. ■

Survey of rice nematodes in deepwater rice fields

Suree Sukapanpotharam, Luechai Arayarungsarit, Chalit Setabutara, and Praphas Weerapat, Rice Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand

A survey of parasitic nematodes in deepwater rice fields was conducted in Thailand from January 1979 to January 1980.

Samples of soil and plant materials were collected from farmers' fields at nine sites in Ayuthaya and two in Prajinburi province at four times: before planting, before the floodwaters rose (about 45 days after seeding), after the floodwaters receded (about 3 mo after seeding), and at harvest.

Each sample was randomly collected from four spots in a field and then composited. Nematodes were extracted from soil, roots, and leaves by Baermann's funnel technique and identified at the Plant Pathology Division. The genera identified are listed in Table 1.

Only *Hirschmanniella*, *Tylenchorhynchus*, and *Meloidogyne* were abundant in the soil. They represented 11.4, 41.5, and 47.1% of the total population sampled (Table 2). *Hirschmanniella* was abundant in the

1. Symptoms produced on the grass host *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv.